

INTERACTIVE METHODS ARE AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF INCREASING STUDENTS' CREATIVITY

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Abstract. *In the article, the development of the educational system, educational technologies for increasing the activity of students at school, the effectiveness of using interactive educational methods to prevent students from getting bored and to fully express their opinions in the development of the educational field, Methods that activate students and encourage them to think independently, where the student is at the center of the educational process, are discussed. Information is given about the most popular interactive educational methods today.*

Keywords: *creativity, interactive graphic organizers, educational efficiency, modern pedagogical technologies, boomerang, gallery, zig-zag, assessment technology, motivation, communicative competences, interactive technology, cluster, cognitive map, brainstorming, role play games, reflection, metaplan card, associative thought.*

Creativity (creativity) (lat. creation - creativeness, creativity) - the ability to create something new, unique, create an artistic form, a mental process that leads to thinking, ideas and solutions; creative ability, which describes a person's readiness to create and accept new ideas. Creativity is strengthened in the activity of the student, it gives an opportunity to achieve effective results, to create innovations, to determine the creative directions of one's activity.

There are a number of interactive methods and technologies for developing students' creative abilities and talents. Including "Cluster", "Staircase", "Perception map", "Role-playing games" and "Brainstorming", "Assessment technology", "Working in small groups", "Reflection" and "Metaplan card" methods. can pass. Designing and applying these methods in the educational process based on the purpose and content of the lesson leads to the following results:

- ✓ students' interest and motivation to study increases;
- ✓ learners are prevented from getting bored and tired in class;
- ✓ the learner develops creative work skills and active thinking;
- ✓ helps to attract new associative thoughts and imagination freely and openly on the topic.

Currently, modern teaching methods are widely used in the educational process. The use of modern teaching methods leads to high efficiency in the teaching process. It is appropriate to choose these methods based on the didactic task of each lesson. While preserving the traditional form of the lesson, enriching it with various methods that activate the activity of the students will lead to an increase in the level of mastery of the students.

Today, in the world, methods that form the basis of great experience in the use of modern pedagogical technologies guaranteeing the effectiveness of the educational process are called interactive methods. Interactive educational methods are currently the most common and widely used methods in all types of educational institutions. At the same time, there are many types of interactive educational methods, suitable for the purposes of implementing almost all tasks of the educational process. In practice, it is possible to select the ones suitable for specific purposes and

use them accordingly. This situation has created the problem of choosing the right interactive educational methods for the realization of certain goals.

For this purpose, the lesson process should be organized rationally, the teacher should increase the interest of the learners and constantly encourage their activity in the educational process, divide the educational material into small pieces, and open their contents intellectually. It is required to use methods such as attack, small group work, debate, problem situation, guided text, project, role play and encourage learners to do practical exercises independently.

When choosing interactive methods of teaching, the purpose of education, the number and opportunities of students, the educational and material conditions of the educational institution, the duration of education, the pedagogical skills of the teacher, etc. are taken into account.

Interactive methods mean methods that activate learners and encourage them to think independently, with the learner at the center of the educational process. When these methods are used, the teacher invites the learner to actively participate. The learner is involved throughout the process. The benefits of a learner-centered approach include:

- ✓ high motivation of the learner;
- ✓ study-learning with higher educational efficiency;
- ✓ alignment of the educational process with the goals and needs of the learner;
- ✓ consideration of previously acquired knowledge;
- ✓ support of the learner's initiative and responsibility;
- ✓ creation of conditions for two-way feedback.

✓ Careful study and practical application of each interactive method used in educational practice expands the thinking of students and has a positive effect on finding the right solution to the problem. Increases creativity and activity of students. When various theoretical and practical problems are analyzed through interactive methods, the expansion and deepening of the knowledge, skills, and abilities of students is achieved.

✓ It is clear from the above that it is necessary to properly analyze the interactive educational methods and classify them on this basis. Below we present general comments on this issue.

✓ When classifying these methods, they can be divided into interactive methods, interactive educational strategies, and interactive graphic organizers.

Currently, the most popular interactive educational methods are:

1. **Interactive methods:** "Case-study" (or "Educational cases"), "Blister survey", "Modeling", "Creative work", "Problematic education", etc.

2. **Interactive educational strategies.** "Boomerang", "Muzyorar", "Brainstorm", "Gallery", "Zig-zag", "Stairs", "Snowball" and so on. **When distinguishing interactive educational strategies from the composition of interactive educational methods, the approach to organizing group work is based on the fact that, in a certain sense, it is compared to strategic planning. In fact, these strategies are more related to interactive educational methods, and there are no other differences between them.**

3. **Interactive graphic organizers:** "Concept chart", "Insert", "Cluster", "Fish skeleton", "BBB", "Venn diagram", "T-table", "Why?", "How?" and b. The separation of interactive graphic organizers is based on the fact that the main ideas in such classes are expressed in written form in various graphic forms. In fact, working with these graphic organizers is more related to interactive educational methods, and there are no other differences between them.

Interactive educational methods are often used simultaneously with various forms of training technologies. The use of these methods increases the activity of training participants and improves the effectiveness of education.

Thus, the process of professional education in higher educational institutions is carried out within the framework of a multifaceted integrated system organized in accordance with modern forms and methods of teaching. In this case, each form fulfills the tasks set for itself, but the set of forms and methods forms a single didactic complex. The implementation of this didactic complex is determined by the psychological and pedagogical laws of the educational process.

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